

A Statistical, Quantum Mechanical and Acoustic Study of Liquids[†]

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Modern liquid state theories deal with various aspects of liquids and solutions. Some of the methods used in tackling the problems that confront the chemist have been described in this short review, which incidentally give the tremendous progress made in the application of these theories to liquids and solutions. This paper reviews the progress made in this field including some of the contributions made by the author and his group.

CHEMISTS deal extensively with liquids and solutions. The application of equilibrium and non-equilibrium statistical mechanics to liquids¹⁻⁸, solutions⁹, liquid metals¹⁰⁻¹⁵, alloys¹⁶⁻²⁰ fused salts²¹⁻²⁵ and to such complex mixtures like emulsions^{26,27} is a strong proof of the importance of this discipline in the investigations of chemical problems. The primary object of these studies is to obtain both equilibrium and non-equilibrium properties of liquids in terms of inter-molecular forces.

The earlier theories are partly phenomenological in character. Thus, the surface tension and compressibility is connected by a two parametric equation and can be written as^{10,8-110}

$$Y = \left(\frac{A}{\beta\tau}\right)^\tau \quad (1)$$

where, A and τ are found to be general constants nearly equal to 0.021 atm⁻¹ (erg s⁻²) ^{τ} and 1.624, respectively.

Further, $C_1 \equiv \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial\rho} (1/\beta\tau)\right]_\tau$ first used by Born and was extensively investigated by Rao and his group, its connection to various potential parameters and intermolecular force constants. Thus for the potential function,

$$U(r) = A r^{-n} - B a^{-m} - C a^{-p} \quad (2)$$

C_1 is given by¹¹¹

$$C_1 = \frac{1}{3} \frac{[Rm(n-m)(n+m+6) + p(n-p)(n+p+6)]}{Rm(n-m) + p(n-p)} \quad (3)$$

where, R is the gas constant.

Further, the molecular diameter, σ is related to C_1 through the δ parameter as¹¹²⁻¹¹⁵

$$\frac{(3C_1 - 1)}{2} \equiv \delta \quad (4)$$

$$\text{and } \sigma = (\delta - 1)\delta^{-1} V^{1/3} N^{-1/3} \quad (5)$$

It is also connected to the velocity of sound, U_1 , at various pressures as⁴⁶

$$U_1 = Cp^\lambda \quad (6)$$

$$\text{where, } \lambda \equiv \frac{C_1 - 1}{2} \quad (7)$$

Similarly, assuming a polynomial to represent the pressure of a fluid as

$$P = \frac{RT}{V} + \frac{B_2}{V^2} + \frac{B_3}{V^3} + \frac{B_4}{V^4} \quad (8)$$

one can obtain a relation between the compressibility and vapour pressure fluid as¹¹⁷

$$\frac{\beta_\tau RT}{V_1} \left[6 \ln \left(\frac{RT}{pV_1} \right) - 11 \right] = 1 \quad (9)$$

where V_1 is the molar volume of the liquid, β_τ is the isothermal compressibility and p is the vapour pressure at temperature T.

However, the thermodynamic and other equilibrium properties, according to modern statistical mechanical theories can be simply obtained through the use of the structure factor (SF)¹⁰⁻²⁷ or its Fourier transformation (FT), namely the radial distribution function (RDF)^{1,2}. It is possible to obtain through perturbation theories equation of state²⁸⁻³¹, through which equilibrium properties can be obtained. Further, the static SF and RDF can be used to obtain the transport properties³²⁻³⁶, thus pointing to the fact that one can obtain all properties of liquids through a unified approach.

Significant structure theory :

Much of the work done on significant structure theory is based on a large number of parameters and hence, has been criticised and is not used now. However, the theory can be utilised to predict the properties of liquids³⁷⁻⁴² even though it may be considered empirical.

Distribution function theories :

The most notable contribution in the study of liquids is the analytical solution for the direct corre-

[†] Dedicated to Professor Sadhan Basu on the occasion of his 65th birthday.

lation function (DCF) obtained with the hard sphere potential function for the non-linear Percus-Yevick integral equation by Wertheim⁴³ and Thiele⁴⁴. The DCF is defined through the equation known as the Ornstein-Zernike's equation written as

$$h(r_{12}) = C(r_{12}) + \rho \int c(r_{13}) \cdot h(r_{32}) dr_3 \quad (10)$$

where, $h(r_{12})$ is the total correlation function and is equal to $[g(r) - 1]$ and $C(r_{12})$ is the DCF.

Atomic liquids :

Through the use of the mean spherical model approximation (MSMA) the structure function can be obtained. The MSMA is defined as

$$C(r) = C_{ref}(r) \quad r \leq \sigma \quad (11)$$

$$= \frac{u(r)}{K_B T} \quad r > \sigma \quad (12)$$

where, $C_{ref}(r)$ is the reference DCF which is generally taken as the hard sphere system and $u(r)$ is the potential function. Extensive work done by the author and his students has shown that in the case of metals the square-well potential is an appropriate potential^{1,2,4,5-51}. Even in the case of non-metallic liquids the square-well potential gives reasonably good results. The SF defined in the case of atomic liquids can be written as

$$S(k) = \frac{1}{1 - \rho \bar{C}(k)} \quad (13)$$

where, $\bar{C}(k)$ is the FT of $C(r)$, the DCF.

The structure factor in the improved MSMA requires that the DCF outside the core is given by

$$C(r) = -\beta u_1(r) g_0(r) + \frac{1}{2} \beta^2 u_1^2 g_0(r) \quad (14)$$

instead of that given in equation (12), where $u_1(r)$ is the perturbing potential and $g_0(r)$ is the reference hard sphere RDF. Extensive calculations in the evaluation of SF of several metals have been made by Rao and Sen¹⁵ and Rao and Joardar¹⁸ with this approximation.

In the long wave limit the SF is related to compressibility as

$$S(0) = \rho k_B T \beta_T \quad (15)$$

where, β_T is the isothermal compressibility and the rest of symbols have their usual significance. From equation (15) it is possible to formulate the equation of state through the random phase approximation (RPA) and one can then obtain various thermodynamic properties^{18,28-31,46}. In addition, it is possible to obtain from the SF the potential function of the molecules⁴⁷⁻⁵⁰. Besides, the DCF can also be obtained from the SF through the use of the following equation

$$C(r) = \frac{1}{2\pi^2 \rho r} \int_0^\infty \frac{k[S(k) - 1]}{S(k)} \sin kr \, dk \quad (16)$$

From the DCF it is possible to obtain potential parameters. Such calculation have been made for methane by Rao and Murty⁵¹.

Higher order structural correlation functions :

The pressure derivative of the SF is related to higher order correlation functions⁵²⁻⁵⁴. Rao and Murty⁵³ and Rao and Sen^{54,55} calculated these pressure coefficients in the $\rho^{-1/3}$ model in the MSMA. Expressions for the higher order SF's in the long wave limit are also derived⁵²⁻⁵⁴.

Self consistent approximation and evaluation of the virial coefficients :

The RDF at the medium concentrations can be expressed in a power series as a function of density, ρ , as

$$g(r) = e^{-\beta u(r)} [1 + \rho g_1(r) + \rho^2 g_2(r) + \dots] \quad (17)$$

where the $g_1(r)$ are connected to various virial coefficients of the fluid. These $g_1(r)$ can be computed topologically, and using the self consistent requirement of the pressure and compressibility equations of state one can calculate the virial coefficients⁵⁶⁻⁶⁰.

Partial structure factors (PSF) in alloys :

It is not always possible to obtain PSF's of alloys from experiment. Hence, model potential calculations become imperative. Further, it is found that the potential parameters obtained for pure liquid metals can be used lucratively for obtaining the PSF's¹⁶⁻²⁰. From these partials one can obtain the Bhatia-Thornton partial structures which are related to the thermodynamic activities of the constituents of the alloy. Even when compound formation is there the PSF's and also the total SF can be obtained. We give in Figs. 1-4 the partials and the total structure factors of Gold-Caesium alloy which forms a compound and considerable volume contraction⁶¹ takes place in the compound formation. The agreement even in this case is quite satisfactory.

Triplet correlation functions in alloys can be calculated with model potentials. Such calculations of triplet correlation functions were performed in Na-K alloy by Rao and Murty¹¹⁶.

Fused salts :

From a consideration of the various forms of $C_{ij}(r)$, Rao and Pal²¹⁻²⁴ postulated that even for charged hard spheres of unequal diameter the form of $C_{ij}(r)$ remains the same inside the core as for charged hard spheres

Fig. 1. Gold-caesium alloy-gold-gold partial structure at 500°, 70% at Cs.

Fig. 2. Gold-caesium alloy-caesium-caesium partial structure at 500°.

Fig. 8. Gold-caesium alloy-gold-caesium partial structures at 500°, 70% at Ca.

Fig. 4. Gold-caesium alloy-total structure factor at 500°.

of equal diameter. The latter have the same form as neutral and hard spheres. Thus, they concluded

that the DCF of charged hard spheres should have the form as

$$C_{ij}(r) = \alpha^1 + \beta^1 r + \gamma^1 r^2 \quad (18)$$

where, α^1 , β^1 and γ^1 are functions of packing fraction and charge on the spheres and the details of these parameters are explained in the original papers²¹⁻²⁴. Thus by suitably choosing σ and hence, $\eta \equiv \left(\frac{\pi\rho\sigma^3}{6}\right)$ it is possible to generate $S_{ij}(k)$ the partial SF's in good agreement with experiment. We give below in Figs. 5 and 6 the partial structures and their corresponding RDF's of NaI²⁵. We give

Fig. 5. Partial structure factors, $S_{ij}(k)$ of molten NaI.

in Fig. 7 the FT of the partial direct correlation function of KCl²².

Fig. 6. Partial radial distribution function $g_{ij}(r)$ of molten NaI.

Fig. 7. Direct correlation function $C_{ij}(k)$ for molten KCl.

Charged hard sphere model :

The charged hard sphere model can be used to calculate in the one component plasma approximation the SF's of metals with the DCF obtained by Palmer and Weeks¹²¹ who perturbed the charged hard spheres with a coulomb potential. For accurate description of electron correlation one has to take into consideration the k dependent dielectric constant and the so-called linear screening optimisation approximation. Detailed calculations have been performed for the evaluation of the SF of noble metals¹¹⁹. These calculations can be extended for the evaluation of like charge SF's in the case of molten salts¹²⁰.

Molecular liquids :

The study of molecular liquids is rather involved because of the orientation problem of the atoms. Both intra- and inter-molecular interactions have to be considered. In the beginning, the orientation model approach was used⁶⁸⁻⁶⁹ but recently the so-called reference interaction site model (RISM) approach⁷⁰⁻⁷² and its various modification are

being applied. Cummings and Stell⁷³ gave an excellent description of the various interaction site models for molecular liquids.

Pseudo-potential (Ps) study of liquid metals :

Gibbs-Bogoliubov's inequality principle in the thermodynamic perturbation method allows the determination of the equilibrium properties with the use of an appropriate pseudopotential⁷⁴⁻⁷⁵. The SF can also be generated^{76, 77}. However, the method is computer time consuming as the diameters have to be determined by a variation technique and does not yield accurate results.

Light scattering and frequency-dependent SF in the hydrodynamic limit :

Mountain⁷⁸ developed a single relaxation time mechanism for the evaluation of spectral distribution of scattered light. This method fails when absorption occurs by more than one mechanism. The single relaxation mechanism has been applied to toluene to obtain the intensity spectrum. From these calculations, the Brillouin shifts and phonon velocity can also be calculated⁷⁹.

Turbidity and light-scattering :

The application of statistical mechanics to emulsions, colloidal solutions and macromolecules is fast gaining momentum. The hard sphere model and the MSMA perturbation version are being used to obtain turbidity and the SF and other associated properties in these solutions. Using the compressibility data of the emulsions one can obtain the potential energy parameter⁸⁰. The partial structures as well as turbidities⁸⁰⁻⁸² can then be predicted. When we are dealing with globular protein solutions the predictions can be very accurate. The recent studies of colloids and emulsions with the help of neutron and X-ray diffraction studies give structural correlation and form factors of these solutions containing macromolecules⁸³. The intensities and the various structural features of the micelle at different concentrations can be predicted⁸⁴.

Acoustic aspects of the study of liquids :

Visco-elastic properties of liquids : Schofield⁸⁵ in an important paper obtained expressions for the elastic moduli of liquids through the method of fluctuation. It was shown that C_{11} , C_{12} and C_{44} are related to the I_1 and I_2 integrals, defined by

$$I_1 = \frac{\rho}{2k_B T} \int g(r)r \frac{du(r)}{dr} dr \quad (19)$$

$$I_2 = \frac{\rho}{2k_B T} \int g(r)r^2 \frac{d^2u(r)}{dr^2} dr \quad (20)$$

These equations were applied assuming a square-well potential for several types of liquids⁸⁴. These I_1 and I_2 integrals coupled with Zwanzing and Mountain's equations⁸⁵ along with Lennard-Jonh 6-12 potential was applied to boron trioxide⁸⁶ to arrive at the high frequency moduli. Collins and Raffel⁸⁷ derived expressions for the shear and bulk

viscosities which can also be casted in terms of I_1 and I_2 integrals. The viscosities of B_2O_3 with a L-J 6-12 potential at various temperature⁸⁶ and also several other square-well fluids were computed⁸⁸.

The I_1 and I_2 integrals can also be applied to molten salts and the viscosities η_S and η_B and high frequency moduli, namely G_∞ and K_∞ can be obtained⁸⁹. The Collin-Raffels equations for viscosities can be usefully applied through the use of RDF and its derivative^{84,90,91}.

Collins and Raffel from hydrodynamic considerations derived an expression for the friction coefficient⁸⁷, which is given by

$$\gamma^2 = \frac{\rho}{3m} \int \Delta^2 u(r) g(r) dr \quad (21)$$

Through the use of an effective mass concept first introduced by Egelstaff⁹², the diffusion coefficients for the square-well and hard sphere fluids can be calculated^{84,91}.

Non-linear acoustics : The measurement of ultrasonic propagation constants become unreliable when sound waves of finite amplitude pass through the fluids because of non-linear effects, like acoustic streaming and distortion of wave form due to attenuation of high frequency components, since attenuation is proportional to f^2 . The non-linear terms B, A and C can be obtained through the pressure derivative of sound velocity and they can be evaluated through the use of Rao-Keer constant⁹³, $C_1 = \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial P} (1/\beta_T) \right]_T$. These acoustic parameters have been evaluated for square-well fluids and compared with experiment⁹⁴.

Shear and structural relaxation times in liquids : Through the use of Caranhan and Starlings equation of state and Zwanzig-Mountain's equation for G_∞ and K_∞ the high frequency shear and bulk moduli respectively, one can derive expressions for the shear relaxation times⁹⁵⁻⁹⁷. When the liquid possesses a permanent dipole moment one has to use a modified form of the equation of state in the evaluation of high frequency bulk modulus⁹⁸.

Some applications of the liquid state equations to solids :

The resemblance between liquids and solids is very similar. Extensive applications of solid state theories to derive liquid state properties is in long use⁹⁹⁻¹⁰³. The present equations of liquids state even though crudely assumes isotropy is solids as is true in liquids will be highly interesting to apply and find out what type of results are obtained. Assuming a hard sphere model, extensive calculations have been done by Rao and Das Gupta¹⁰⁴ in the evaluation of SOE's for a variety of solids. Also, the pressure derivatives of SOE's can be calculated through the pressure derivatives of I_1 and I_2 integrals.

An expression has been arrived at for C_{111} in terms of packing fraction η and $S(0)$ the long wave

limit of SF. Thus, one can calculate C_{111} through equation (22).

$$C_{111} = - \left[5 + \frac{4(1-\eta)^2 (2+\eta)\eta}{S(0) (1+2\eta)^2} \right] C_{11} \quad (22)$$

All these calculated values compare favourably with the experiment.

Space limitations do not permit the author to describe the detailed applications of modern liquid state theories to electrochemical¹⁰⁵ and various other physicochemical problems^{106,107} that one confronts in liquid state.

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